

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

A REVIEW OF MECHANICAL TESTING OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Ian McEnteggart
Composites Market Manager
Instron

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Topics

- Laminate Bulk Properties
 - Tensile
 - Compression
 - Shear
- Compression After Impact
- Composite Testing System Solution
- Fatigue Testing

Testing to Characterise Bulk Properties

Orthotropic material:

- Tensile moduli/strengths: $E_{1t}, E_{2t}, E_{3t}, S_{1t}, S_{2t}, S_{3t}$
- Compressive moduli/strengths: $E_{1c}, E_{2c}, E_{3c}, S_{1c}, S_{2c}, S_{3c}$
- Shear moduli/strengths: $G_{12}, G_{23}, G_{13}, S_{12}, S_{23}, S_{13}$
- Poisson's ratios: $\nu_{12}, \nu_{23}, \nu_{13}$

Tension

0° Fibre dominant property.
90° Matrix & Fibre-Matrix adhesion

Compression: Matrix dominant property.
 Dependant on the stiffness and adhesion qualities of the resin being able to prevent bucking of the fibres

Shear: Matrix dominant property,
 transferring stresses across the composite.

Conditioning

e.g. Humidity

Test Conditions

Hi/Low Temp

In-Plane Tensile

ASTM D 3039

EN 2561/2597

ISO 527-4/5

- Specimens may have variety of layups and orientations e.g. 0/90° for UD.
- Strain measurement using strain gauges, clip-on or Non-contact extensometers.
- Strain gauges and Non-contact extensometer allow measurement of strain at failure.
- Averaging axial extensometers and pairs of strain gauges can compensate for mis-alignment and give more consistent modulus results
- Biaxial extensometer or axial + transverse strain gauges required for determination of Poisson's ratio

Non-contact Video Extensometer

Strain Gauges

Averaging Biaxial Extensometer

In-Plane Tensile – Gripping

- Tabbed thermoset matrix specimens
 - Can be gripped in a range of manual or hydraulic grips with serrated jaw faces.
- Un-tabbed thermoplastic matrix specimens
 - Bonding of tabs to thermoplastic composites can be difficult because of low adhesion.
 - Bonding of tabs is time consuming and expensive and unlikely to be accepted by high volume users of composites e.g. automotive.
 - Gripping un-tabbed thermoplastic specimens with fine pattern, or carbide coated faces, can give good results [1]. It is likely that recommendations regarding this approach will appear in future revisions of ISO 527-4/5.
- Pultruded UD materials
 - These important materials are usually produced in the form of round rods. They are very strong in the axial direction but weak in the transverse direction and this makes gripping a challenge.
 - A common solution is to use a long gripping length and a semi-circular grip profile matched to the specimen diameter.

In-plane Tensile Testing - Alignment

What do we mean by “Alignment”?

Why is Alignment Important?

Ductile Metal Test Piece

- Misalignment introduces uneven stress distribution
- Metal yields in high stress region but continues to carry load
- Stress redistributes reducing the effect of misalignment on test results

Fibre Composite Test Piece

- Misalignment introduces uneven stress distribution
- Fibres in high stress region fail
- Stress in remaining fibres increases causing rapid failure.
- Misalignment has a significant effect on Test results

Achieving & Verifying Alignment

ASTM D 3039

ASTM E1012

ISO 527-4/5

- Testing Machine

- High Axial & Lateral Stiffness
- Guided
- Alignment Fixture (below)

- Alignment is usually verified under load using strain gauged “specimens”
- Examples of Strain Gauged Specimens and measurement system display:

ISO 527-4/5

- Gripping techniques

- Moving body grip provides repeatable jaw engagement
- Side to Side Symmetrical wedge “pocket” controls jaw face alignment
- Front-Back Symmetrical body maintains accurate alignment under load.
- Specimen Stops ensure accurate specimen location

NOTE: Design principles apply to both Manual and Powered (e.g. hydraulic grips)

Nadcap Flat 4 Gage Option

Through thickness Tensile

- Specimen bonded to metal studs
- Strain gauges required for modulus determination

Compression Testing

End-loaded Supported Gauge Section

ASTM D695 (Modified)

ASTM D 6484 (OHC)*

END FORCE

CLAMP FORCE

SHEAR FORCE

Combined loading Unsupported Gauge Section

ASTM D 6614

ASTM D3410 (ITTRI)

ISO 14126, AITM 1-0008

Wyoming Modified Celanese

Shear Loaded Unsupported Gauge Section

*NOTE: ASTM D6484 also allows shear loading

Inter-laminar Shear Testing

SBS (Short Beam Shear) - Various

- Apparent ILS Strength only (no modulus)
- Simple rectangular specimen
- Widely used QC test for materials and parts

DBS (Double Beam Shear) – ISO 1927

- “True” ILS Strength and modulus
- Simple rectangular specimen
- [2], [3]

ASTM D7078

ASTM D5379

Vee-notched Shear methods – ASTM D 5379, D7078

- “True” ILS Strength and modulus
- Complex specimen
- Used for establishing materials design data

Typical shear strain distribution

In Plane Shear

In Plane Shear (IPS) - Various

Test set up similar to tensile test but specimen has fiber directions of +/- 45 degrees

Simple test but not a pure shear stress state (shear + axial tension)

Rail Shear – ASTM 4255

Rectangular specimen is clamped between rails.

Not a pure shear stress state

Shear Frame – ISO 20337 [4]

Pure shear loading

Large shear strains (>5%)

Expensive specimen preparation

Complex test fixture and procedure

Compression After Impact (CAI)

A defined level of damage (e.g. Energy or BVID) is introduced into a laminate plate using a drop weight tower and the reduction in strength of the material assessed by performing an end loaded compression test on the plate

Impact set up

Typical Drop Weight Machine

ASTM D 7137

AITM 1-0010

Typical CAI Test - Force v Displacement

Composites Testing System Solution – Combining many different test types on one machine

Precise Grip Alignment

Alignment Fixture

Load cell with 1000:1 range

Temperature Chamber

Compression to ASTM D695 etc.

“Piggy back” Compression Platens with Spherical seats

CAI

Composites Fatigue

- Fatigue – degradation due to repeated cyclic stresses
- Original commercial uptake by aerospace and wind energy sector
- Demand for future automotive development
- Fatigue properties usually presented in the form of an S-N plot

BMW Megacity Vehicle carbon fiber cockpit model

From: Smith: "Principles of Materials Science & Engineering," McGraw Hill (1986)

Composites Fatigue & Temperature

- Fatigue test specimens generate heat internally. For metals this is usually insignificant
- For composites can be severe (>10C)
- Varies with stress level and damage history
- Solution is to control the test frequency throughout the test
- Improves throughput and reduces variability
 - Case study: $31 \pm 7 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ reduced to $30 \pm 0.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
 - 27.5% time saving

Log fit: $\sigma_c = -a \ln(N) + c$	4 Hz (excluding outliers)	Adaptive frequency
Gradient	2.886	2.651
Intercept (% UTS)	104.4 %	100.7 %
Fit quality ("R ² ")	0.931	0.966
Predicted Stress at 10 ⁷ cycles (%UTS)	57.9 %	57.9 %
Predicted Stress at 10 ⁸ cycles (%UTS)	51.2 %	51.8 %
Equivalent Test Time (Continuous machine time)	55 days	40 days

References

1. Presentation to ISO TC61/SC13/WG2 Unbonded tabs or gripping condition without tabs using fine grip face as informative annex (Annex C) Tsuyoshi Matsuo¹, Masaki Hojo², Kazuro Kageyama³. ³The University of Tokyo ² Kyoto University
2. ISO 19927:2018 Fibre-reinforced plastic composites -- Determination of interlaminar strength and modulus by double beam shear test
3. THE 20TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS Double Beam Shear (DBS) – a new test method for determining interlaminar shear properties of composite laminates G. Zhou, P.H. Nash, J. Whitaker and N. Jones
4. ISO 20337:2018 Fibre-reinforced plastic composites -- Shear test method using a shear frame for the determination of the in-plane shear stress/shear strain response and shear modulus